

Concept of Health, Illness and Disease in Phalewas, Parbat District

Prepared by: Sujan Sharma Poudel

Central Department of Anthropology, Tribhuvan University,
Kritipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

Subject: Medical Anthropology

Submitted to: Prof. Dr. Kapil Babu Dahal

Date: 27th April, 2025

Introduction

Phalewas, a peaceful semi-rural in the Phalewas Municipality, Parbat District, Gandaki Province, Nepal has its own unique way of understanding health, illness, and disease. Based on a combination of traditional beliefs, natural living, and modern science, people's experiences reflect how rural communities adapt over time. In this assignment, I have tried to explain these concepts based on my own memories, experiences, and the changes I have observed in my community.

Concept of Health

Health in my hometown is seen as complete well-being – not just the absence of illness. Traditionally, it is about being strong enough to work, celebrate festivals, and take care of the family. Eating fresh homegrown food, drinking spring water, and living close to nature is believed to maintain good health.

During my childhood, if I woke up scared at night, my parents would take me to a local priest called Maaela Baa. He would perform a ritual called Sato Fukne, blowing mantras and using kharani (fire ash) on me. Within minutes, I would feel fine. Maaela Baa was not just a priest; he meditated for hours in his worship room every day and lived a very simple, pure life. Sadly, he is no longer with us, but his memory lives on.

Earlier, health education mainly came through radio programs. Nowadays, with almost 80% internet access in our area, people rely more on social media like YouTube, TikTok, and Facebook for health tips. Many even buy Ayurvedic tonics online. In case of minor illnesses, people use homeopathic remedies; for major

diseases, they seek allopathic, Ayurvedic, and sometimes homeopathic treatments together.

Our area has one small hospital, one health post, and one health clinic. Most people first visit the health post, then Ayurveda, and finally the hospital if needed. According to financial capacity, people travel to Kushma, Pokhara, Chitwan, or Kathmandu for bigger treatments.

Concept of Illness

In Phalewas, illness is often seen as a disturbance not only in the body but in spiritual or social balance. Sometimes illness is believed to be caused by angered ancestors or broken taboos.

I remember some families near my home used to suffer both health-wise and financially. They would consult a special priest who could 'connect with ancestors' in rituals called Pitri Bakaune to find the cause and solution.

Modern education has made people aware that illnesses like fever or diarrhea are caused by germs or hygiene problems. Yet, when modern medicine doesn't work quickly, many still turn back to rituals and traditional healing. The youth today often use internet content for health advice, while older people, influenced by social media, sometimes trust what they see online without verifying.

Concept of Disease

Disease is now mostly understood scientifically as infections or biological problems. Earlier, diseases like typhoid and pneumonia

were feared as curses. Today, people know about bacteria, viruses, and prevention methods. Government campaigns, vaccination drives, and awareness through media have helped.

However, sometimes medicines run short in the health posts, even though the Nepal government tries to provide free medicines for many diseases. Because of this, private clinics have become popular, offering quick service and home visits. People trust local health professionals more because they are accessible.

Our location on plain land between hills helps us — mosquito-borne diseases and snake bites are rare here. I also remember my grandmother carefully choosing vegetables depending on the family's health — believing that certain foods generate more heat or coldness in the body. Her teachings still hold meaning for me today.

Migration has now increased from our village. Many large houses remain closed, and families visit only occasionally, like we do now. Youths engage quickly with new health trends through the internet, while the elderly community slowly adapts through social media.

Conclusion

In Phalewas, health, illness, and disease are understood through a mix of traditional beliefs and modern science. While scientific medicine is more trusted today, the cultural practices, respect for natural remedies, and community healing rituals still continue. The balance between tradition and progress defines the health culture of my community.